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ABSTRACT

IFAST Task 12.1 is studying novel and important applications of particle accelerators in the health, environmental, imaging and radioisotope production areas and has identified those with the most potential. For these, it has developed strategies for delivering these applications. This report will describe the applications and the strategies for delivering them.

I.FAST Consortium, 2024

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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1 Introduction

Particle accelerators have been extensively used for many years for a wide range of applications, including cancer treatment, polymer modification, sterilisation of medical products, radioisotope production, imaging, phyto-sanitation, food treatment, etc. These exploit the unique features of the accelerated beams and the control an accelerator provides. Nevertheless, accelerators have a much greater potential that is currently not being fully exploited. This is for many reasons, including a lack of knowledge in industry of what benefits they could bring, the perceived and real cost of the technology, under-performance for some applications, the absence of the skills required to assess the potential for a specific industry and to implement the technology and concerns over safety and regulation.

Task 12.1 has been trying to address these issues in two ways. The first is to select a number of novel applications of accelerators with the most potential. These are in the areas of health, the treatment of environmental contamination, imaging and radioisotope production. The second is to examine and address the main barriers in industry to the introduction of accelerators.

This document describes the novel applications identified and the strategies for delivering them in practice. The applications are separated into the health, environmental, imaging and radioisotope production areas.

It also presents the general barriers to the adoption of accelerators by industry and summarises the progress in analysing and overcoming these barriers.

2 Task 12.1.2 – Novel Forms of Radiotherapy

2.1 VHEE RT

Radiation Therapy (RT) has progressed rapidly, with the development of new technologies and innovation leading to remarkable improvements, but still there are suboptimal outcomes and remaining limitations due to radiation resistant tumours, normal tissue complications and metastasis spread, amongst others.

The most frequently used modality of RT uses high-energy (6 to 10 MV) photons produced by electron linear accelerators (linacs). More than 15,000 electron linacs are currently used worldwide to treat patients. The main fundamental advance in this type of RT has been the use of image guided beam delivery utilizing conventional clinical dose rates (0.5-20 Gy/min). This technique has provided physicians with their best options for improving this critical tool in cancer care, allowing the ability to preferentially target tumours while minimizing the collateral dose to the surrounding normal tissues. Despite all these advances, the treatment of many primary and metastatic tumours remains a challenge as the therapeutic window between tumour eradication and normal tissue complications is narrow.

Now, more than 70 years after the initial idea of using proton and heavier ion therapy, hadron therapy has reached the critical time for transitioning from a limited number of specialized institutions to many particle-therapy centres worldwide. Currently, proton therapy is growing with over 100 HT facilities in the clinical practice and many are under construction or planning, but the impact is still rather small.

More recently, the idea of investigating the use of very high-energy (50-250 MeV) electron (VHEE) beams for RT has gained interest. By increasing electron energies up to 50 - 250 MeV, deeper tissue penetration is possible. The original idea to use electrons in the energy range 50 - 250 MeV for radiotherapy was first proposed by DesRosiers in 2000 [2].

The main advantages of VHEE beams over photons are related to the fact that 1) small diameter VHEE beams can be scanned and focused relatively easily, thereby producing finer resolution for intensity modulated treatments than photon beams. Also, VHEE beams are relatively insensitive to tissue heterogeneities [1], unlike protons for example, which are inherently range sensitive [1]. This allows increasing the therapeutic index of radiation therapy that is dependent on spatial dose distribution. 2) accelerators can be constructed at significantly lower cost compared to the current installations required for proton beam delivery and presents an interesting and possibly cost-effective option to treat cancer. 3) VHEE beam machine can conceivably operate at very high dose rates possibly compatible with the generation of the “FLASH effect” (i.e., to elicit normal tissue sparing and tumour killing).

The recent studies involving the ultra-high dose rate (UHDR) delivery (mean dose rate above 100 Gy/s) of ionizing radiation and termed FLASH radiotherapy (FLASH-RT) have uncovered some surprising and unexpected therapeutic benefits and has caused tremendous excitement in the radio-oncology field as it may revolutionize modern day RT [3]. Noteworthy too is the fact that the “FLASH effect” was and continues to be defined *in vivo*, a feature that portends its rapid clinical implementation and utility. This represents fundamentally a new prospect for increasing the therapeutic index of RT. Indeed, most of the preclinical data demonstrating the increased therapeutic index of FLASH has been using a single fraction of RT and Intermediate Energy Electron (IEE) beams (6 MeV), that do not allow to treat deep seated tumours and trigger large lateral penumbra. This problem can be solved by using VHEE beams (> 50 MeV).

2.1 ACCELERATORS AND ACCELERATOR TECHNOLOGIES FOR VHEE RT

Today and after three decades of research in linear colliders on the Japanese Linear Collider (JLC) [5], the Next Linear Collider (NLC) [6], the Compact Linear Collider (CLIC) [7] and more recently the Cool Copper Collider (C³) [8], it is possible to have compact high-gradient linacs (> 100 MV/m) based on Radio Frequency (RF) accelerating structures (AS), which make a compact VHEE radiation therapy accelerator a reality (Figure 4). Considerable research and development programs have been carried out under the framework of these High Energy Physics (HEP) Colliders projects to obtain the demanding performances of such accelerators. An example is the CLIC linac: an accelerating gradient of 100 MV/m, low breakdown rate, micron-tolerance alignment and a high RF-to-beam efficiency

(around 30%) are envisaged [9-12]. Furthermore, the use of novel accelerator techniques such as Laser Plasma Accelerator (LPA) is also starting to be applied in the VHEE field.

Dedicated VHEE experimental studies have been realized using Normal Conducting (NC) linac based accelerator facilities in NLTA at SLAC and CLEAR at CERN, giving very promising results for the use of VHEE electron beams. Studies are currently being made at CLEAR [20], AWA at ANL [23], PITZ facility at DESY (Zeuthen) [24], ARES facility at DESY (in Hamburg) [25] and, in the near future, at the CLARA facility at Daresbury Laboratory [21, 22]. Superconducting RF (SC) linac technology is also used at the ELBE [13] Center of High Power Radiation Sources at HZDR in Dresden.

Furthermore some experimental tests have been carried out with LPA sources, mainly laser driven, at ELBE-DRACO in HZDR [13], in the LOA in the Institut Polytechnique de Paris [14], the SCAPA facility [15] in the University of Strathclyde and the Istituto Nazionale di Ottica (INO) at Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR) in Pisa [16], amongst others. In particular for FLASH with electron beams, biological studies have been carried out at intermediate-energies with the Kinetron linac [17] and more recently with the eRT6-Oriatron linac at CHUV [3], the ElectronFlash in the Institute Curie (IC) at Orsay or the similar ELF ElectronFlash in Antwerpen [18, 19]. Experimental studies are also ongoing at very high-energies at CLEAR at CERN [20].

Recent advances in **RF accelerator technology**, especially in the high-gradient RF structures where more than 100 MeV/m are now achievable in the lab environment, are transforming the landscape for VHEE RT. This requires beam energies between 50-200 MeV, an improved dose conformity and scaling to higher dose rates, in the case of the FLASH-RT where >50 Gy/s are needed. Novel high gradient technologies could enable ultra-compact structures, with higher repetition rates and higher currents. An international R&D global effort is being made by labs such as CERN, INFN, KEK, MIT, UCLA, LANL, SLAC, AWA-AN, university groups such as the Tsinghua University HG lab and industry partners and are focused towards:

- Material origin and purity, surface treatments, manufacturing technology
- Consistency and reproducibility of test results.

Some recent promising R&D are:

- The distributed coupling accelerator developed at SLAC [26] to more efficiently and uniformly distribute the RF power into the AS and minimise electrical breakdown.
- The use of cryogenic copper is transforming the linac design offering a new frontier from the perspective of beam brightness, overall efficiency, peak RF power requirements, and overall costs. Operation at 77 K (liquid nitrogen) results in a minor decrease in efficiency for establishing gradients with a dramatic reduction in cost and increase in performance. Experiments have shown increased conductivity and hardness enabling higher gradients and an increase in quality factor by 2.5.
- Another approach for the next generation of compact, efficient and high performance VHEE accelerators is the use of higher frequency millimetric waves (~100 GHz) and higher repetition rates using THz sources.

Concerning the **LPA technologies** for medical applications, the main challenges are:

- Beam performance and availability
- Consistency and reproducibility of test results.

These issues are currently the subject of a wide global study and are highlighted in the EU networks: EUPRAXIA [27] or I.FAST [28].

In both cases, robust and more compact global facilities must be developed to adapt the facilities to a clinical environment.

2.2 RADIOBIOLOGY AND CLINICAL IMPLICATIONS

VHEE beams exhibit several promising features for RT. They have sufficient penetrative ability to treat deep-seated tumours (at depths of 30 cm or more) with reduced entrance doses compared to photons and reduced penumbra spreading. The high charge-to-mass ratio of electrons allows for rapid scanning and focused delivery within the patient, further minimizing dose to healthy tissues. VHEE beams also demonstrate relative insensitivity to changes in patient geometry and inhomogeneities, enhancing their suitability for treatment. VHEE therapy requires compact and high-gradient linear accelerator (linac) solutions to accommodate existing treatment suites and minimize space constraints. These linacs need to be reliable, affordable, and capable of accelerating electrons to energies higher than those currently used in clinical environments. However, until recently, the radiobiology and preclinical experiments were limited by the availability of VHEE beams.

There are indeed similar limitations for FLASH research and development, as at present there are only a limited number of existing facilities able to operate and deliver doses at ultra-high dose rates. Since fractionated RT regimens are the standard of care for the treatment of solid tumours, it was essential to evaluate the impact of fractionation and assess whether FLASH-RT when delivered in fractionated regimen still spares normal tissue and eradicates tumours. Recent evidence suggests that this is the case as the hypo-fractionated FLASH regimen maintained tumour response and neurocognitive sparing [4] and preserved synaptic functionality in the brain.

In summary, this differential response between normal tissue and tumours triggered by FLASH combined with VHEE characteristics might offer a unique opportunity for the field of radiation oncology to enhance tumour control in a safe and more efficacious manner. In addition, as hypo-fractionated regimens are becoming the standard of care for the treatment of a variety of tumour types, the capability to dose escalate with FLASH radiotherapy facilitates these approaches, and minimizes the number of patient visits and should minimise the cost of healthcare and maximise patient throughput. As a result, the interest in VHEE has been growing rapidly.

The limited access to VHEE beams for experimental research in radiochemistry and radiobiology is expected to be resolved soon as more beam lines become available for the scientific community and are coupled with biology laboratories. This will pave the way for new fields of investigation, including radiochemistry experiments which have already begun [29].

At the biological level, further investigations are needed both in the field of VHEE and FLASH-VHEE. To ensure the safe and reliable translation of VHEE and FLASH VHEE strategies into clinical settings, it is imperative to establish consistent and comparable irradiation conditions. VHEE beams provide a unique opportunity to investigate the biological effects of ultra-high dose rates ($>10^8$ Gy/s) and extremely brief exposure times (nano-second), whereas proton and photon FLASH beams have dose rates that are limited and typically in the range of a few hundreds of Gy/s at most. Therefore, VHEE beams may be the better option for studying the biological effects of ultra-high dose rates and ultra-short exposure times. Simultaneously, our scientific community will benefit from new biological models and high-throughput investigation provided by integrated biological systems and multiomic studies.

2.3 FUTURE OUTLOOK AND STRATEGY FOR DELIVERY

Although VHEE beams show promise, several challenges remain. Further studies and experiments are necessary to optimize dose delivery methods and reduce the entrance dose, potentially through quadrupole magnet focusing. Additionally, the development of image-guided radiation therapy (IGRT) specific to VHEE treatments is crucial, considering the unique requirements and constraints of delivering treatment at ultra-high dose rates.

From the accelerator technology point of view, an important point is to assess the possibility of focusing [30] and scanning transversely the beam, thereby overcoming the disadvantages associated in the past with low and intermediate energy electron and photon beam irradiation. Stability, reliability and repeatability are other mandatory ingredients for accelerators to be operated in a medical environment.

The major challenge for VHEE-FLASH is the delivery of a very high dose-rate, possibly over a large area, providing a uniform dose distribution throughout the target. Also, the parameter window in which the FLASH effect takes place has still to be thoroughly defined, as well as its effectiveness as a function of the physical parameters of the electron beam. This, together with a clear understanding of the underlying biological processes, will likely prove to be essential in order to fully optimize the FLASH RT technique. Finally, of particular importance, is the development of reliable on-line dosimetry for very high dose rates, a regime not adapted to the current standard dosimetry techniques for RT. Ionization chambers, routinely used in medical linacs, suffer from nonlinear effects at very high dose rates, and in order to get reliable measurements R&D is needed to develop novel ion chamber types, or explore alternative possibilities such as solid state detectors or the use of calibrated beam diagnostics.

All this asks for a large beam test activity, in order to experimentally characterize VHEE beams and their ability to produce the FLASH effect and provide a test bed for the associated technologies. It is also important to compare the properties of the electron beams depending on the way they are produced (RF linac or LPA technologies). A number of experimental test facilities are already or will soon be available to perform these ambitious objectives.

Regarding the linac design in the energy range of interest for VHEE applications, there are different possibilities offering the desired performance and compactness with different degrees of technology maturity. The S-band technology is the most mature one, HG compact linacs of this type are already available from various industrial partners. The C-band and X-band RF linacs are less mature and are mainly constructed in the labs, with the help of industry, but these offer the prospect of high gradient acceleration and hence will allow high energies to be achieved over a relatively short linac. In recent times, a considerable effort is being made from the industrialization point of view. Furthermore, future facilities, as exemplified by the CERN-CHUV facility, are on the horizon. In summary an important R&D effort to apply these technologies in the medical field is ongoing and, if successful, could be a step further in the quest for compact and efficient VHEE RT in the range of hundred MeV.

For achieving these aims, a synergistic and multidisciplinary research effort based on accelerator technology, as well as physical and radiobiological comparisons to see how well VHEE can meet the current assumptions and become a clinical reality, is needed.

In summary, VHEE RT has the potential to revolutionize cancer treatment by offering improved dose distribution and reduced radiation to healthy tissues. Advances in compact and high-gradient linac solutions, treatment planning, and dose optimization techniques are key to translating VHEE theory into clinical practice. Continued research and development efforts are needed to overcome challenges and optimize VHEE radiotherapy for the benefit of cancer patients.

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3 Task 12.1.3 - Environmental Applications of Accelerators

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Technologies based on electron accelerators aimed at ensuring the safety of gaseous and liquid effluents discharged to the environment have been developed. Emerging technologies are now focused to encourage ballast water and ship diesel off-gases treatment to follow recent standards introduced by the International Maritime Organization (IMO). The remarkable R&D works concerning sludge hygenization, marine diesel off gases treatment and ballast water treatment have been developed in the frame of ARIES and IFAST projects. In present times, with increasing emphasis on circular economies, municipal wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are considered resource recovery facilities. The targeted resources are water, biogas, and sludge, organic residuals containing nutrients and elements needed by plants (nitrogen and phosphorus). Therefore, electron beam technologies are an important supplement to conventional technologies in preserving a clean environment for our global future.

3.2 IMPORTANCE OF THE PROBLEM

Rapid population growth combined with industrialization, urbanization, and energy intensive lifestyles has resulted in severe problems to the environment, especially in large cities. In many countries where industry is concentrated in urban areas, severe air and water pollution problems have arisen in most of the large cities. Therefore, the pollution control has become an important subject in the field of environmental engineering with electron accelerator use [1,2].

3.2.1 Air Pollution

Fossil fuel combustion leads to acidic pollutants such as SO₂, NO_x, HCl and PAH emission.

Recently, there has been significant concern about the air pollution from marine sources that currently utilize low quality diesel fuels. Three new regulations aimed at reducing maritime greenhouse gas emissions and the environmental impact of ships were introduced on 1st January 2023 by the IMO. As a result, research and development projects have focused heavily on creating a cost-effective technology that can clean off-gases with high efficiency. Exhausts from marine engines contain nitrogen, oxygen, carbon dioxide and water vapour as well as nitrogen oxides, sulfur oxides, carbon monoxide, various hydrocarbons and complex particulate matter. The maritime transporters usually use heavy fuel oil (HFO) with a high content of sulfur, which naturally leads to the three main pollutants derived from shipping: nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulfur oxides (SO_x) and particulate matter (PM). Around 15% of global NO_x and 5–8% of SO_x emissions are attributable to ocean-going ships. SO₂ emission as a smog component is a precursor to acid rain and it can have a negative influence on plant life as well as on wider ecosystems.

3.2.2 Water Pollution

North America and Europe generate around 67 billion m³ of wastewater each year. That gives 231 m³ per capita in the case of the U.S. However, Africa's wastewater discharge is around 95m³ per capita annually and is significantly lower than North America and Europe. A total of 56% of the household wastewater globally was properly treated in 2020. No effective technologies have yet been developed to remove all the contaminants simultaneously, even though some contaminants have been shown to decompose to a certain degree in selected processes.

The main means of transport for global trade is ocean shipping and nowadays around 90% of traded goods are carried over the waves. The discharge of sea water used for ballasting ships poses a threat to coastal ecosystems. In 2004, the IMO developed the Convention on the Control and Management of Ship's Ballast Water (BWM Convention), which provides a uniform legal regulation of the ballast water problem around the world. A ship, before entering a shipyard, has to replace the ballast water (with its antibiological treatment) in open waters. However, some waters still remain, together with solid state sediments containing biological contamination. When the ship is placed on the dry dock for maintenance (repair, painting, etc.), this ballast water has to be discharged. The treatment technologies are applied to reduce microbiological contamination.

3.2.3 Sewage Sludge

Sludge is a byproduct that constitutes the largest volume of all other byproducts obtained in wastewater treatment plants. Thus, quick development and implementation in industrial practice of sludge valorization and utilization technologies is required, where high nutrient content must be taken into account. Also, the occurrence of a variety of pathogens in sewage sludge is a matter of concern, even in the case of developed countries. The use of untreated sludge or wastewater in agricultural activities poses a serious risk of bacterial and parasitic infection in human beings. To overcome such issues, the application of ionizing radiation processing, especially electron beam (EB), can be considered a promising method. Its effectiveness in pathogen removal has been proven by researchers. Additionally, ionizing radiation technologies in sewage sludge treatment enhance the efficiency of the methane fermentation process. In this technical solution, a notably effective additional step would be the use of EB irradiation, combined with conventional wastewater treatment, to achieve efficient removal of pollutants.

3.3 DESCRIPTION OF POLLUTION CONTROL ACCELERATOR BASED TECHNOLOGIES

The treatment of off-gases from diesel ship diesel generators require, due to high NO_x concentration, the application of other modified technology. A new, hybrid technology is based on the concept of combining two methods used to clean up the exhaust gases: Electron Beam (EB) and Wet Scrubbing. A new emerging hybrid technology that couples the Electron Beam with the reduced size wet scrubbing methods may provide an answer to reducing emissions from the marine shipping industry. Tests have been carried out in the frame of ARIES Innovative Project and INCT, being a developer of the process, received a patent [3]. Recent tests have illustrated the possibility of process applications to treat the polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) and volatile organic compounds (VOC), including chlorinated VOCs, present in off-gases in trace concentrations. In addition, the

concept of greenhouse gas CO₂ removal has also been developed and a patent application for this has been submitted to Polish Patent Office.

A large number of substances present in wastewater such as hard surfactants, lignins, and pesticides cannot be degraded by conventional biochemical methods. Thus, they escape from decomposition in biological treatment. Biodegradation quality of wastewater depends on the oxidation level and structure of pollutants. Preliminary oxidation and fragmentation of biologically resistant molecules contribute to the improvement of their biodegradability. EB processing of wastewater is non-chemical and uses fast formation of short-lived reactive radicals that can interact with a wide range of pollutants [4]. The most important advantage of radiation technologies, especially those using electron beams, is the relatively short time period required compared to other advanced oxidation processes (AOPs), which allows satisfactory results to be obtained. Diclofenac (DCF) degradation in aqueous solution under electron beam irradiation after nanobubbling treatment was studied and compared with treatments using nanobubbling or EB irradiation alone. It was found that the removal efficiency of DCF increased by increasing the adsorbed dose, and it depended on the initial concentration of DCF in solution, being higher for the lower concentrations. Furthermore, when using the nanobubbling treatment alone, about 16% of the DCF was removed from the aqueous solution due to the OH radicals generated during the process, while 99% could be achieved by adding EB treatment [5]. The major barrier to radiation technologies are economic factors, especially those related to the large investment costs necessary at the plant construction stage. This subject has been studied in IFAST as well.

Another possible accelerator application is ballast water treatment. On the laboratory scale, an EB hybrid method has been developed in the frame of IFAST project with technical and financial contribution of REMONTOWA SHIPBUILDING S.A. The tests have been performed for 10 ships arriving from the different regions. For the controlled pathogens, the D₁₀ dose [kGy] resulting in a 10-fold reduction in the population is as follows: *Vibrio cholerae*, *V. parahaemolyticus*, *V. vulnificus*, D₁₀ = 0.1 kGy ; *E. coli* D₁₀ = 0.5 kGy ; *Enterococci* D₁₀ = 0.6 kGy. The lethal effect of ionizing radiation on marine organisms of different size was also confirmed. The biological species and solid particulate matter were separated from the water stream by mechanical screening and membrane processes can be used to recirculate water for technological use.

The municipal water treatment plant, excess sludge to be used as organic fertilizer must be hygienized [6]. The use of EB treatments allows for the complete elimination of nematodes and parasitic eggs (*Ascaris sp.*, *Trichuris sp.*, *Toxocara sp.*, ATT) and the practical elimination of pathogens, such as contagious bacterial contamination and *Coliform* titer (decreased by three orders of magnitude for dose 1 kGy), *Clostridium perfringens* titer (decreased by five orders of magnitude for a dose of 1 kGy). The irradiated sludge being pathogen free can then be beneficially used as manure in the agricultural fields as it is rich in nutrients required for the soil. Since the irradiated sludge is free from bacteria, this can also be used as a medium for growing useful bacteria like *rhizobium* and *azetobacter* to produce biofertilizers, which can be used to enhance the crop yields. A new concept “zero energy” biogas plant is based on the construction of a complex system consisting of a biogas plant and an electron accelerator in the biofertilizer manufacturing line. Digested material (in which organic solids were decomposed into stable substances) originating from the methane fermentation of sewage sludge is irradiated to remove all pathogens using an electron beam from an accelerator powered by electric energy obtained from burning biogas in a co-generator. The product is a high quality, biologically

safe fertilizer. As a result of Task 12.2, the IFAST-MS59 basic engineering validated by design office has been prepared [7].

3.4 ACCELERATORS FOR ENVIRONMENTAL APPLICATIONS

In the field of radiation processing technology, microwave source-powered linear accelerators, single resonant cavity accelerators and direct current accelerators are being applied. The differences between the types of accelerators depend on the methods of generating accelerated electrons. To create electrical fields, two fundamental techniques have been used: direct-acting high-voltage power supplies for accelerators, and radio or microwave frequency generators for resonators, which use the electrical component of electromagnetic waves to accelerate particles (figure 1).

Figure 1: Electron accelerators applied in radiation processing: (A) direct high voltage accelerators; (B) single cavity radiofrequency accelerators; (C) linear microwave accelerators. 1 – electron gun, 2 –focusing coil, 3 – scanning electromagnet, 4 - foil window.

A variety of industrial electron accelerators can now provide electron energies from 0.3 MeV to more than 10 MeV with average beam power capabilities up to 700 kW. The creation of new, highly powerful electron accelerators that can be utilized for online processing of enormous flow streams of liquid or gaseous contaminants was a unique input for the technological advance’s application. The accelerators were set up in an extremely efficient installation and used for the process of treatment of wastewater and off-gas. However, to make this method of production competitive, further advancements in accelerator technology are required for the implementation of these processes. That is because the machines need to have a great deal of power, high energy consumption performance, and a high degree of dependability to work in challenging industrial sectors.

3.5 STRATEGY FOR ENVIRONMENTAL APPLICATIONS

Argonne National Laboratory [1] held a workshop exploring the energy and ecological uses of accelerators. R&D thrusts and the implications these advancements would have upon increasing

accelerator capacity and efficiency targets are discussed in the workshop’s conclusions, which are provided in the publication as a table. The following are the main obstacles to the widespread use of technology connected to accelerators; (i) the absence of accelerator devices that are capable of operating at full-scale industrial levels, which tend to be at least ten times beyond the current state of the art; (ii) the necessity of developing accelerator systems that can be significantly reliable and efficient while remaining competitive with existing technological advances; (iii) the lack of pilot levels applications for these new technologies to show their efficiency and efficacy. It is feasible to compare these needs with the market condition currently using specified data.

		Target Accelerator Capabilities			
		Demo/pilot scale (0.5 MW, 0.5-1.5 MeV)	MW-class DC system (1 MW, 1-2 MeV)	MW-class high-energy (1 MW, 30 MeV)	Ten MW-class high-energy (10 MW, 30 MeV)
R&D Needs	DC Systems: HV, high current	3	3	3	3
	NCRF Linac Systems: structures, performance	3	3	3	2
	SRF Linac Systems: structures, performance	2	3	3	3
	Beam Dynamics	2	3	3	3
	Electron Sources	2	3	3	3
	RF Power Systems: higher efficiency, lower cost	3	3	3	3
	SRF materials and cavity fabrication	3	3	3	3
	RF delivery components	3	3	3	3
	Beam windows	3	2	2	3
	Portability, field-ability	2	2	2	2
	System-level demonstration	2	3	3	3
	Commercialization viability	2	3	3	3

	Very important
	Somewhat important
	Not important or not applicable

The absence of pilot-level applications to demonstrate the effectiveness and efficiency of these new technologies is important. It is possible to use the provided data to compare these needs with the state of the market at this time. More complicated scenarios are associated with ecological applications that require high power, excellent electrical efficiency, and low-cost accelerators. Superconducting system-based solutions provided some hope, but their advantages and disadvantages were not thoroughly investigated on an industrial scale [8,9.10.11]. They need magnet cooling systems, so they might not reach their predicted efficiency ratings. Utilizing clean energy sources to produce the electricity required to run accelerators could help solve the issue.

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4 12.1.4 – Accelerator Imaging

4.1 INTRODUCTION

Accelerators play a key role in many imaging technologies. Accelerators are able to generate X-rays via Bremsstrahlung radiation by accelerating electrons into a target, by inverse Compton scattering of photons (ICS) or by particle induced X-ray emission (PIXE) using protons and these can be used for security imaging, imaging of artwork or cultural heritage imaging. As well as imaging with X-ray we can image with neutrons allowing penetration into denser or thicker subjects.

Of these imaging technologies Bremsstrahlung is the most mature having been around for decades, however as detector technologies and computer reconstruction improves technologies need to be adapted. Different application and detector technologies currently under development require multiple angles, shorter pulses, faster energy switching or continuous operation (currently all sources are pulsed) with each requiring a new accelerator development. Nuclear resonances can be excited to

identify particular substances but this requires either enormous photon fluxes or narrowband sources, neither of which can be satisfied by Bremsstrahlung. To meet this new demand ICS is required, but they must also be compact. For thinner objects like paintings, or cave art X-ray transmission imaging would provide little contrast so instead the objects are bombarded by protons to induce X-ray emission from the object itself, the spectrum of which can provide information about the paints used. Such imaging has been used to reveal original artworks that were later painted over. For denser cargo we use the scattering of neutrons for imaging.

4.2 ACCELERATOR IMAGING

4.2.1 Importance

We live in an uncertain world and borders are continually under threat. In order to secure international borders and checkpoints its necessary to have advanced imaging technologies that can see through shipping containers and cargo to inspect what is inside. While a key target is the smuggling of guns, bombs or drugs another concern facing border security is smuggling for the purposes of tax avoidance. Cars, money, and tobacco are routinely smuggled across borders to avoid paying tax cost. Tobacco smuggling alone cost the EU 10 Billion Euros in lost revenue. As technology has evolved so has the threats that need to be detected, one example of this is Li-Ion batteries which are both a target for future smugglers and a risk of explosion, but conventional X-ray scanners are not optimised for detecting them. The use of multiple views is expected to improve the capability to scan batteries but this would be prohibitively expensive without new accelerator technologies. Using a combination of neutron and gamma-ray detectors and deep learning algorithms, substances can be identified down to their atomic level making it easier to detect certain explosives. Another concern is special nuclear materials, which look like any other dense material in X-ray scanners. Such materials need to be detected to stop smuggling of such materials into rogue states or the transport of dirty bombs. In order to detect these Nuclear Resonance Fluorescence is required that will undergo specific emission under narrowband X-ray irradiation at the correct energy such that by scanning the energy these resonances can be measured to identify the material.

4.2.2 Goal to demonstrate imaging use

The sub-task network includes industry who can directly take developments to market. As the accelerator is acting as the radiation source in an imaging system, it needs to be integrated with a detector array for use in imaging.

The sub-task has studied the use of fast neutron imaging at multiple energies and Dynaxion have demonstrated the potential of this technique in a mini-project.

Another area of interest is multi-view X-ray cargo scanning, and Lancaster have been working with Rapiscan to simulate image processing for such a system and evaluating the effectiveness of the approach.

Meanwhile the Movable Accelerator for Cultural Heritage In-situ Non-destructive Analysis (MACHINA) project in Florence is working with CERN to develop a mobile RFQ to test its use with artwork. While Ion Beam Analysis like PIXE has long been used with artwork these have always

been large immobile systems meaning it is only suitable for artwork that can be moved. For Frescos and cave paintings that cannot be moved a mobile system is required.

4.3 STRATEGY TO REACH THESE GOALS

The network is focussed on three core areas

- Advanced X-ray and neutron cargo screening
- Mobile Ion Beam Analysis systems for cultural heritage imaging
- Imaging using inverse Compton sources

Most of the activities to date have focussed on the first two core areas as these are at a higher technology readiness level while the ICS is still in the proof of fundamental principles stage as the beam requirements for an ICS are very demanding and require a far larger scale accelerator.

The network had a call to fund mini-projects. One project from Dynaxion was selected for funding. Fast neutron imaging is a growing field of interest for non-destructive testing (NDT) and security screening. Due to its high penetration capabilities and specificity for certain elements it is able to make images of items that no other imaging techniques (such as X-ray imaging) can.

This project had two main aims:

- Produce high quality fast neutron images of relevant objects to enhance the adoption of this imaging technique,
- Show that using multiple energies for the imaging of objects will provide additional information about the contents of the object, similarly as multi-energy imaging with X-rays.

Dynaxion has completed this mini-project and thereby demonstrated the potential of the technique.

5 12.1.5 – Radiopharmaceutical Production

5.1 INTRODUCTION

The ongoing evolution of medicine has been profoundly transformed by the introduction of radioisotopes, which have dramatically enhanced both diagnostic and therapeutic practices. These radioactive substances, which emit alpha, beta, or gamma particles, have become indispensable in various medical applications. From early disease detection to precision-targeted treatments, radioisotopes have broken through traditional boundaries, establishing themselves as vital tools in the quest for improved patient health and well-being.

In the field of diagnostics, the integration of radioisotopes into advanced imaging technologies has provided unprecedented insights into the human body's physiology and structure. Techniques such as Single Photon Emission Computed Tomography (SPECT) and Positron Emission Tomography (PET) utilize gamma and positron emissions, respectively, to monitor metabolic processes and offer detailed visualization of organs and tissues. SPECT generates high-resolution, three-dimensional images that are critical for the early detection of conditions like cardiovascular and neurological diseases. Meanwhile, PET scans, often using radioisotopes like fluorine-18, capture real-time metabolic

activity, offering crucial data for the early diagnosis and tracking of cancers and neurological disorders.

In therapeutic applications, radioisotopes emitting alpha and beta particles have significantly expanded treatment options. Alpha particles, known for their high energy and limited penetration range, are ideal for highly targeted therapies, such as those used in specific cancer treatments. Beta-emitting radioisotopes, with their broader tissue range, are employed in treating various conditions, including thyroid diseases and certain cancers. This targeted approach allows for the delivery of therapeutic doses directly to diseased tissues, minimizing collateral damage to healthy surrounding cells.

The advent of theragnostic—combining diagnostics and therapy—has paved the way for highly personalized medical approaches. The same radioisotopes used for diagnostic imaging can also deliver precise therapeutic interventions. This dual functionality is revolutionizing disease management, enabling customized treatments that address the unique needs of each patient.

5.2 STATE OF ART

The field of nuclear medicine has experienced remarkable advancements, unlocking a new era of opportunities to tackle clinical challenges with greater diagnostic accuracy and more efficient therapeutic interventions. The development of innovative radiopharmaceuticals, coupled with the optimized synthesis of key radioisotopes, has been pivotal in driving these breakthroughs, paving the way for more effective medical treatments.

Significant technological advancements, particularly in **high-energy and high-current accelerators** [1][2], have emerged as powerful tools for radioisotope production, complementing existing methods. This progress has expanded the availability of promising radionuclides, such as gallium-68 [3], copper-64 [4], Erbium-169 and zirconium-89 [5]. The development of robust high-power electron accelerators has also led to the production of therapeutic radionuclides like scandium-47, actinium-225, and copper-67 [6]. Additionally, alternative approaches using both electron [7] and proton [8] accelerators are being explored for the large-scale production of molybdenum-99/technetium-99m, which remains the most widely used diagnostic radionuclide.

Beta emitters, including iodine-131, lutetium-177 [9], samarium-153, and yttrium-90 [10], have become essential components of therapeutic nuclear medicine. The successful application of radiolabelled peptides and enzyme inhibitors in cancer therapy has driven a significant increase in global demand for lutetium-177 over the past decade. Targeted alpha therapy is another critical area of interest, capturing the focus of radioisotope producers, researchers, and nuclear medicine practitioners. Alongside radium-223, several other alpha-emitting radionuclides, such as actinium-225, astatine-211, bismuth-212, bismuth-213, lead-212, thorium-227, and terbium-149, are being actively investigated for their potential in advancing radiopharmaceutical applications. The current demand for actinium-225 far exceeds its supply, prompting research groups worldwide to focus on the efficient production of these highly sought-after alpha-emitting isotopes [11] [12] [13]

Figure 2: Daily production of Ac-225 through different production methods across various laboratories

The landscape of radiopharmaceuticals has continuously evolved, transitioning from simple ionic radioiodine to complex coordination compounds of technetium-99m. Today, a range of PET radioligands, as well as experimental theragnostic and therapeutic agents, are under investigation for their potential clinical applications. This evolution has been marked by several key milestones, including the development of new radiochemistry techniques that allow for the labelling of various ligands with different radionuclides, advancements in automation, and the availability of non-clinical assessment tools. These achievements are the result of significant contributions from scientists across multiple disciplines.

The concept of theragnostic radioisotopes, which combine both diagnostic and therapeutic properties in a single radioisotope or a compatible pair, offers a promising framework for future developments in the medical use of radionuclides. When paired with biomolecules that target specific cellular sites, theragnostic radionuclides provide a powerful approach to clinically significant radionuclide therapy. This strategy not only enhances diagnostic accuracy, dosimetry, and post-therapy planning but also embodies the principles of personalized medicine, bringing us closer to a future where medical treatments are tailored to the unique needs of each patient.

Increasing the availability of cerium-134 for imaging could benefit the medical use of therapeutic radioactive isotopes. These isotopes emit alpha particles that target cancer and other diseases. Cerium-134 is chemically like actinium-225 and thorium-227. This means cerium-134 can be attached to the same targeting systems as the therapeutic isotopes. Using the same targeting systems means that cerium-134 diagnostics and actinium-225 and thorium-227 treatments will behave in similar ways in the body. This allows scientists to use cerium-134 to view and monitor actinium-225 and thorium-227 as they work. The result is more information for medical researchers and clinicians treating disease.

5.3 MARKER NEEDS

Some of the most important marker needs are:

- Development of innovative routes of production of therapeutic and diagnostic radionuclides, looking into reactor-based and alternative methods, including accelerator-based as well as separation / purification methods, also considering waste management options, nuclear security and proliferation concerns. Many research groups are investigating alternative methods to produce some radioisotopes without the use of a nuclear reactor. Some studies are supported by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) through projects like: “Accelerator based Alternatives to Non-HEU production of Mo-99/Tc-99m”.
- Development of optimised irradiation targets, that are interchangeable to allow use within the whole supply network, and prioritizing production with raw and source materials which are available and sustainable.
- Development of recommendations for implementing clinical trials involving radiopharmaceuticals, including the development of individual/specific organ dosimetry for the therapeutic applications (in target and non-target tissues). Urgent need for achieving convergence on radiation dosimetry and safety aspects, especially of new RI used, or proposed, for targeted therapy and for theragnostic. High energy gammas are present in the decay scheme of many RI under exploration. Positron emission is often only a certain % of the decay of some RI. These impact radiation dosimetry aspects. Thus, it is imperative to take the entire decay scheme of RI into consideration for dosimetry, efficacy and safety purposes.
- Ensuring an adequate supply of radioisotopes for further research, clinical trials and clinical use with full implementation of radiation protection measures and with reduction of costs along the whole supply chain.
- Lack of accessibility and availability of many useful products in some countries, apart for the issue of their high cost in many cases. **Russia’s invasion of Ukraine** has brought new urgency to search for new production capacity for critical isotopes, some of which are solely sourced from Russia or rely on a precursor from the country [14].
- The demand for alpha-emitting radionuclides significantly exceeds their supply. Numerous research groups worldwide are working on efficient production.

5.4 NOVEL ACCELERATORS FOR ISOTOPES PRODUCTION

Significant technological advancements in the field of high-energy and high-current accelerators have emerged as transformative tools to produce radioisotopes. These innovations not only complement but also enhance traditional methods, paving the way for more efficient and economically viable production processes.

5.4.1 Electron Accelerators for Photonuclear Reactions

Electron accelerators have proven to be highly effective in photonuclear reactions, offering several advantages over classical production methods [1], [11], [15]. They enable the production of a range of important radionuclides with higher specific activities and/or at reduced costs. Key isotopes produced using electron accelerators include:

- Scandium-47 (^{47}Sc): Essential for targeted cancer therapies due to its ability to deliver radiation precisely to tumour sites.

- Titanium-44 (^{44}Ti): Valuable for PET imaging, particularly in the study of metabolic processes and neurological conditions.
- Copper-67 (^{67}Cu): Used in cancer therapy and molecular imaging, providing high therapeutic efficacy.
- Palladium-103 (^{103}Pd): Important for prostate cancer treatment and as a diagnostic tool.
- Tin-117m ($^{117\text{m}}\text{Sn}$): Employed in gamma imaging and targeted radiotherapy.
- Erbium-169 (^{169}Er): Utilized in various radiotherapy applications and diagnostic imaging.
- Lead-195m ($^{195\text{m}}\text{Pb}$): Suitable for therapeutic and diagnostic purposes due to its unique decay properties.
- Actinium-225 (^{225}Ac): Crucial for targeted alpha therapy, especially in treating specific cancers.

The use of electron accelerators for these productions ensures a high specific activity and cost-effectiveness, making them a valuable addition to existing production methods [11].

5.4.2 New Proton Accelerators for Isotope Production

Proton accelerators, particularly those operating in the energy range of 70 to 150 MeV with a proton current of approximately 1.0 mA, offer significant benefits for radionuclide production [2], [16] [17] [18] [19]. This energy range is underdeveloped globally, providing a unique opportunity for advancing the field. The advantages of proton accelerators include:

- **Rare Isotope Beam (RIB) Research:** Proton accelerators enable the production of highly sought-after radionuclides for RIB physics research. This range supports the creation of several valuable isotopes and parent nuclei essential for various applications.
- **Production of Radionuclides:** Proton bombardment of a thorium target yields a range of valuable products, including:
 - Actinium-225 (^{225}Ac): Important for targeted alpha therapy in cancer treatment.
 - Bismuth-213 (^{213}Bi): Used in targeted alpha therapy and diagnostics.
 - Radium-225 (^{225}Ra): Utilized in therapy and research applications.
 - Astatine-211 (^{211}At): Applied in targeted cancer therapies and radiopharmaceuticals.
 - Potential to provide: Radium-224 (^{224}Ra): Useful for targeted radiotherapy. Lead-212 (^{212}Pb): Applied in cancer treatment and as a radiotracer. Bismuth-212 (^{212}Bi): Important for targeted alpha therapy and diagnostic imaging.

In summary, the advancements in high-energy electron and proton accelerators represent a significant leap forward in radioisotope production. By leveraging these technologies, we can achieve higher specific activities, reduce production costs, and increase the availability of radionuclides essential for research, clinical applications, and pharmaceutical development. These innovations hold promise for addressing current challenges in radionuclide production and expanding the range of isotopes available for diverse applications.

5.5 STRATEGY TO DELIVER THIS APPLICATION

To effectively deliver the application of high-energy and high-current accelerators for radioisotope production, a comprehensive strategy is required. This strategy should address several key aspects including technology development, infrastructure, collaboration, regulatory compliance, commercialization and education.

5.5.1 Technology Development

a. Accelerator Optimization:

- **High-Energy Electron Accelerators:** Focus on enhancing the design and performance of electron accelerators to increase their efficiency in photonuclear reactions. This includes optimizing beam currents, energy levels, and target interactions to maximize yield and specific activity of produced radionuclides. [1] [11]
- **Proton Accelerators:** Develop and refine proton accelerators operating in the 70 to 150 MeV range. This involves improving beam stability, current capabilities, and energy precision. Special attention should be given to expanding cyclotron capabilities and integrating advanced technologies for better control and efficiency [2].

b. Target Material Research:

- Investigate and develop new materials for targets that can withstand high-energy bombardment and enhance the production yield. This includes exploring novel target designs and materials that can handle higher proton currents and energies.

c. Production Techniques:

- Enhance existing production techniques and develop new methodologies for radionuclide extraction and purification. This involves integrating advanced separation and purification technologies to improve the purity and specific activity of the produced isotopes.

5.5.2 Infrastructure Development

a. Facility Design and Upgrades:

- Invest in the construction and upgrading of accelerator facilities to support high-energy and high-current operations. This includes building or renovating facilities to

accommodate the new accelerators, ensuring they meet safety standards and operational requirements.

b. Maintenance and Support:

- Establish robust maintenance protocols to ensure the continuous operation and longevity of the accelerators. This includes regular servicing, troubleshooting, and upgrades to keep the equipment at peak performance.

5.5.3 Collaboration and Partnerships

a. Academic and Research Institutions:

- Foster collaborations with academic institutions and research organizations to drive innovation and conduct joint research. These partnerships can facilitate the exchange of knowledge, expertise, and resources.

b. Industry Partnerships:

- Engage with industry partners to develop commercial applications and scale up production. Collaboration with pharmaceutical companies and other stakeholders will help in translating technological advancements into practical solutions.

c. International Cooperation:

- Participate in international research initiatives and networks to stay aligned with global advancements and share knowledge. Engage with organizations such as the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) for guidance and support.

5.5.4 Regulatory Compliance and Safety.

a. Regulatory Approval:

- Navigate the regulatory landscape to obtain necessary approvals for the use of new accelerators and radionuclides. Ensure compliance with safety standards and regulations for both the production process and the end use of radionuclides.

b. Safety Integrity Level (SIL):

- **Definition and Implementation:** Implement Safety Integrity Levels (SIL) to ensure the safe operation of accelerators. SIL is a measure of the reliability of safety-related systems and processes. Define and establish SIL requirements for different aspects of accelerator operations, including control systems, emergency shutdown mechanisms, and radiation protection.
- **SIL Assessment:** Conduct thorough assessments to determine the required SIL for each component and system involved in accelerator operation. This involves evaluating the risk associated with potential failures and implementing appropriate safety measures.
- **SIL Compliance:** Ensure that all safety systems and processes meet the defined SIL requirements. Regularly review and update these systems to maintain compliance and address any emerging safety concerns.

5.5.5 Commercialization and Market Integration

a. Market Analysis:

- Conduct a thorough market analysis to identify demand for specific radionuclides and assess potential commercial opportunities. This will guide production priorities and help tailor offerings to meet market needs.

b. Product Development:

- Develop and commercialize radioisotope products, ensuring they meet quality standards and are competitively priced. Work on packaging, distribution, and marketing strategies to effectively reach the target audience.

c. Supply Chain Management:

- Establish a robust supply chain for the distribution of radionuclides. This includes logistics planning, inventory management, and partnerships with distributors to ensure timely and efficient delivery to end-users.

5.5.6 Education and Training

a. Workforce Development:

- Provide training programs and resources for personnel involved in the operation and maintenance of these accelerators. This includes technical training, safety education, and professional development opportunities.

b. Public Awareness:

- Raise awareness about the benefits and applications of high-energy accelerators and radionuclides through outreach and educational initiatives. This can help build support for the technology and foster a better understanding of its impact.

5.6 CONCLUSIONS

The successful delivery of the application of high-energy and high-current accelerators for radioisotope production requires a multifaceted strategy. By focusing on technology development, infrastructure, collaboration, regulatory compliance, commercialization, and education, we can ensure that these advanced tools are effectively utilized to meet growing demands and drive innovation in the field. This comprehensive approach will enable the production of valuable radionuclides with enhanced efficiency, safety, and economic viability.

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6 12.1.6 – Overcoming Obstacles to Accelerator Use

6.1 OBSTACLES PREVENTING ACCELERATOR ADOPTION BY INDUSTRY AND ENVIRONMENT CONTROL

The major barriers to EB technologies broad applications **in industry** are:

- **Economic factors** (investment cost and operational cost):
Now, there are no strict technological limits to design, construct and build accelerators achieving parameters needed for their applications on industrial scale. Many research accelerator laboratories are running machines with parameters largely exceeding industrial needs. Although the technologies are basically available, the cost-criterion moves to the first (or at least one of the top) position(s) since an industrial company must reach a profit within a reasonable time. Therefore, one can identify as the first barrier: **the technologies** that are in principle feasible and proven from existing accelerators (or similar research instrumentation) on laboratory scale **must be available at reasonable cost** before they can be used in machines for industrial and societal applications. Fulfilling of this condition may still need a long-term research and development.
- **Absence of the accelerator-laboratory environment:**
This has two major impacts: (i) global **absence of in-house specialized and auxiliary facilities and equipment for accelerator service and maintenance** and (ii) **absence of in-house accelerator experts and staff for accelerator operation, service and maintenance**. The accelerator-selling company must provide the user with conditions that can fully compensate for the absence of the accelerator-laboratory environment. This can be achieved in several ways (or combination of them): remote customer-support; well-elaborated regular maintenance and service scheme; providing accelerator experts via different schemes (flying experts or keeping some permanent staff directly on-site); offering machines fulfilling extra specifications.
- **Problems of newcomers:**
There are newcomers on both sides: new (potential) users of accelerator technologies and new (potential) industrial companies having an ambition to produce accelerators or their components. Obviously, intensive communication between those two groups is necessary in order to match the users’ needs with the producers’ offer. The producers must know what the customers need and the customers shall know what is feasible and what they can ask for. The universities and research labs shall play a catalysing role in this communication. **Intensive promotion of accelerator technologies is needed.**

The major barrier to EB technologies broad applications **in the field of environment control** are:

- **Economic factors**, especially those related to the large investment costs necessary at the plant construction stage. There have been many attempts at economic analyses concerning both the investment costs and the cost of treating 1 m³ of water/wastewater. Depending on the adopted initial conditions, the costs of treatment of 1 m³ ranged from USD 0.075 to 3.17. Particularly promising are the results indicating an increase in biodegradability after the application of small doses of 1–2 kGy of ionizing radiation. It should be expected that the practical application of radiation technologies in the treatment of water and wastewater can be really helpful for making progress in this field.
- **Lack of high power, low cost and high reliability accelerators** for work in harsh environments. In the last decade, DC Electron Accelerators in the energy range (0.7-2.5 MeV) and power (100-600 kW) have been used for treatment of flue gases and industrial and municipal wastewater. Operation of such accelerators at the industrial plant level have indicated the necessity of further developments and development of energy efficient accelerators in higher energy range (up to 10 MeV). The increase of energy will enable treatment of thicker layers of wastewater due to larger penetration depth of electrons. The 5 MeV electrons can treat about 2 cm of liquid with 1g/cm³ density.

6.2 SOLUTIONS IDENTIFIED

- *The absence of accelerator-laboratory environment* can be compensated by the accelerator-selling company by providing the user with **remote customer-support**. Many diagnostics, maintenance and even operational actions can be done either on-line via internet or at least using diagnostic data transferred via internet (the so-called log-files) or by running special diagnostic tools that can be distributed via internet. The development of the remote customer-support technologies is another important branch of research and technology that must be included in the strategy of industrial and societal applications of accelerators. This is obviously a dedicated branch of IT-technologies and computer science. At the same time, it is a new and attractive area of professional career for young generations of IT-experts on one side and accelerator engineers on the other one. Dedicated educational schemes and study programs are needed to bridge and bring those two expert communities together. They must be able to speak a common language, which means that the IT-experts shall understand basics of accelerator physics and technology and the accelerator experts shall understand the basics of IT. This is clearly a role for academic institutions (mainly universities) to design, offer and run such new interdisciplinary study programs. The **maintenance and service scheme** of the accelerator-selling company is basically a part of the contract between the company and the customer. Offering **machines dedicated for industrial applications** will also help to increase the application of accelerators in industry. However, different performance specifications become crucial in comparison to research accelerators. Namely: **reliability; reproducibility; high duty-factor** (long beam-on times without troubles); **operational simplicity**. An ideal accelerator would be a two-button (START & STOP) machine requiring as little operational complexity as possible. This is the goal the accelerator designers should be aiming at and

small electron accelerators used for cleaning the environment are good candidates for that. This should be the priority of developing them at the moment.

- ***The problems of newcomers*** can be overcome by the intensive promotion of accelerator technologies reached by (i) **education of accelerator physicists and engineers**; (ii) **attracting the specialized high-tech companies** to the market of accelerators and accelerator components; (iii) **attracting potential users** of accelerators from non-accelerator communities (biologists, oncologists; chemists; applied physicists; environmental engineers; food-processing companies; electrical engineers; all possible suppliers of accelerator components and subsystems (IT and computer scientists; RF engineers; high-voltage engineers; control systems; magnets designers; cryogenic engineers; vacuum technologists; etc.) The universities must play a catalyzing and coordinating role in this promotion.
- The main challenge for the next **implementation of EB technologies in the field of environment control** is the **availability of high power, low cost and high reliability accelerators for work in harsh environments**. To treat gases the best solution is to apply transformer accelerators with the electron energy below 1 MeV. However, to treat water and sludge linear accelerators may be the solution. Linear accelerators (linacs) using the room temperature copper RF cavities are attractive for the MeV-scale energy range required for wastewater and sludge treatment. However, these normal conducting RF cavities are constrained to operate at very low RF duty cycle due to high RF heating at the cavity walls. This low RF duty operation usually limits the average e-beam power obtainable from normal conducting linacs to few 10s of kW, making them less viable for high-volume irradiation applications. Superconducting RF cavities made of pure niobium or Nb3Sn, with cryogenic operation near the temperature of 4 K, exhibit extremely small RF wall dissipation (about six orders of magnitude smaller than copper cavities of comparable shape and size), allowing their operation at 100% RF duty cycle (continuous wave or cw operation). SRF cavities can thus produce very high average power e-beams suitable for high-volume irradiation applications. It is also well known that SRF cavities can be more energy and cost efficient compared to copper cavities even after accounting for the energy and cost premium required for their cryogenic operation (Ciovati, 2015).

6.3 RECENT EXAMPLES OF ACCELERATOR USE

- **Industry**. There are now over 2000 high current, electron beam (EB) accelerators being used world-wide in industrial applications, most of which involve polymer processing. In contrast to the use of heat, which transfers only about 5–10% of input energy into energy useful for materials modification, radiation processing is very energy efficient, with 60% or more of the input energy to an accelerator being available for affecting materials. Historic markets, such as the crosslinking of wire and cable jacketing, of heat shrinkable tubings and films, of partial crosslinking of tyre components and of low-energy EB to cure or dry inks and coatings remain strong. Accelerator manufacturers have made equipment more affordable by down-sizing units while maintaining high beam currents. Very powerful accelerators with 700 kW output have made X-ray conversion a practical alternative to the historic use of radioisotopes, mainly cobalt-60, for applications as medical device sterilization. New EB end-uses are emerging,

such as the development of nano-composites and nano-gels and the use of EB processing to facilitate biofuel production. These present opportunities for future research and development. Over the decades, different energy accelerators have been found to be more suitable for different industrial polymer applications:

1. Low-energy (from 120 keV to 300 keV) — printing inks; coatings for paper, wood, metals and plastics; adhesives; multilayer packaging; and surface grafting for membranes.
2. Mid-energy (from 300 keV to 5 MeV) — wire and cable insulation; heat shrinkable tubing and films; fiber modification; polymer blends with nano-particles and with natural polymers.
3. High-energy (from 5 MeV to 10 MeV) — sterilization of medical devices and some pharmaceutical and biological products; treatment of industrial and domestic effluents and sludge; treatment of lignocellulosic materials to produce ethanol biofuels.

- Environment pollution control. Examples of accelerators applications for environmental pollution control were discussed in Task 12.1.3 - Environmental Applications of Accelerators.

6.4 KEY RECOMMENDATIONS

The main challenge for the near future is the availability of high power, low cost and high reliability accelerators for work in harsh environments. It would be extremely advisable for the IFAST Steering Committee to consider as one of the results of this project the construction of a prototype of this type of device in Europe for industrial and environmental applications, starting from 10 MeV and 20 kW machine. Some elements can be prepared using printing technology developed in the frame of IFAST.

The next challenge is for universities. Dedicated educational schemes and study programs are needed to bridge and bring together accelerator designers and engineers with accelerator users. Intensive promotion of accelerator technologies is needed covering: education of accelerator physicists and engineers, attraction of specialized high-tech companies to the market of accelerators and accelerator components; and attraction of potential users of accelerators from non-accelerator communities.

7 Conclusions

IFAST Task 12.1 has identified and studied a range of novel and important applications of accelerators. Most of these are in areas where accelerators are already widely used, in particular health, imaging and radioisotope production. The remainder are in the area of environmental applications, where there have been many studies, but rather few production facilities have been built and there is limited current commercial use, but much potential. For each identified applications, the steps still required before the application can be delivered have been described and the plans for these given. In all cases, there is much interest in doing this work and progress is often only limited by the availability of funding.

The task is also studying the general barriers to the adoption of accelerators by industry, independent of the application area. It has already identified mitigation methods for some of these and will continue to work on the remainder.

8 Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
ATT	intestinal parasites of the genera <i>Ascaris</i> , <i>Toxocara</i> and <i>Trichuris</i>
cfu	colony-forming unit
cw	continuous wave
d.m.	dry mass
DC	direct current
EB (eb)	electron beam
FGD	flue gas desulfurization
HFO	heavy fuel oil
PAH	polyaromatic hydrocarbons
PM	particulate matter
RF	radio frequency
SCR	selective catalytic reduction
VOC	volatile organic pollutants
WWTP	waste water treatment plant